

Supplementary material

“Process mining: a methodology to assess patients’ care pathways and improve health outcomes”

Authors

Carlos Tellería-Orríols†, Santiago Royo-Sierra†, Francisco Estupiñán-Romero†, Javier González-Galindo, Ignacio Oscoz-Villanueva, Asier Ballesteros-Domínguez, Ibai Tamayo, Julián Librero, Berta Ibáñez-Beroiz, Enrique Bernal-Delgado†, on behalf of CONCEPT.

† These authors contributed equally to this work

Scope

This document provides the supplementary material for the manuscript entitled “**Process mining: a methodology to assess patients’ care pathways and improve health outcomes**”. Its primary objective is to offer technical documentation and extended results complementing the study's findings.

This research is framed within the national coordinated project “CONCEPT: Efficiency and effectiveness of chronic care in the Spanish National Health System” (see details [here](#)), lead by Enrique Bernal-Delgado, MD PhD, Senior Researcher in Health Services and Policy Research in the Data Science for Health Services and Policy Research group at the Aragon Health Sciences Institute, IACS.

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Section S1. Glossary of process mining terms

Activities (also known as events) represent each of the contacts between a patient and a healthcare resource or as a consequence of the health care assistance; activities may be, for example, admissions, visits, laboratory tests, imaging tests, surgical interventions, prescriptions, or administrative contacts.

Care pathway (also known as care process, clinical pathways, or care maps) is the representation of the actual care provided to patients; instrumentally, it implies the representation of the sequence of health care activities and interventions to which a patient is exposed, ordered by the time when they took place.

In turn, a **normative pathway** (also known as theoretical pathways) represents the process that a patient with specific characteristics should follow according to evidence or guidance [1],[2].

Path (also known as trace) is the sequence of activities and interventions followed by a single patient over a time period.

The **decision points** represent the place where different paths split out in two or more paths. Discovering the underlying reasons for these paths diversion allows the understanding of whether clinical or administrative decisions on the patients' treatment may (should) be modified to improve outcomes.

Section S2. Description of the study and the cohort

Population and setting

For the purposes of this paper, two patient cohorts were used to illustrate how to use process mining techniques in the evaluation of care pathways (CPW): patients enduring an acute ischemic stroke and patients with diabetes.

This observational retrospective study included virtually all the potential acute stroke incident cases between 2010 to 2022 in Aragon, and in the case of the diabetes cohort, all incident cases diagnosed between 2017 and 2022 in Navarre. The definition of both cohorts can be found in this methodological paper in common data model (CDM) [3],[4], we used two patient cohorts for the construction of two case-studies: 24995 cases in patients enduring an acute ischemic stroke between 2010 to 2022 in Aragon and 11189 incident patients with diabetes (of whom 134 with heart failure) between 2017 to 2022 in Navarre.

Data

This methodological study was built on routine individual longitudinal data from different data sources; in Aragon, the data were extracted upon informed request from BIGAN -<https://bigan.iacs.es/es/inicio>- (established by Executive Order SAN/1355/2018 as an element of the regional health information system); in Navarre, the data were extracted upon informed request by the Methodology-Health Services Research Unit, Navarrabiomed-UPNA from BARDENA -<https://portalsalud.navarra.es/es/w/contenido-bardena->, NASTAT -<https://nastat.navarra.es/es/>-and, ISPLN -<https://www.idisna.es/conocenos/instituciones/instituto-de-salud-publica-de-navarra-> institutions. Depending on the cohort, the study reused administrative and claims data, electronic health records, pharmaceutical bills, hospitalisation and emergency data.

The project, federated in nature, was developed following the ‘*data visiting*’ principle which implied transferring code and executing the data analyses locally keeping the data on premise. Data was extracted, transformed and analysed at data holders level following the above-mentioned CDM specification [3],[4]. Analyses were performed locally after assessing data quality and the aggregated results were shared with the coordination hub that developed the comparative analyses compiling with the results from the different participants (hubs). All the code specification was containerized as a Docker image deployed in each node of the federation. For the purpose of this methodological paper, we show the results of just one of the nodes for each use case. The code for the project can be found in a GitHub repository [5],[6].

The access to data was granted after the approval of the Aragonese and Navarre ethical committee approval (CEICA -*Comité de Ética de la Investigación de la Comunidad Autónoma de Aragón* - C.I. PI19/108; Acta No 10/2023, and CEIM -*Comité de Ética de la Investigación con Medicamentos* - C.I. PI_2019/97 Acta No 489/2019, respectively). The data management plan and protocol can be found in Zenodo [7],[8],[9],[10].

Section S3. Cox multivariate model - Stroke case study

The Cox multivariate model was built with time-to-event (i.e., time-to-death) as the dependent variable and fitness as the main individual predictor. However, other variables are introduced in the model as predictors. We could divide independent factors in two groups:

1) Patient attributes:

- Age (years) as continuous numeric;
- Sex as categorical;
- Several prescriptions (antiarrhythmics, antihypertensive, antiaggregants and fibrinolytics) as boolean;
- Several comorbidities (heart failure, hypertension, diabetes, atrial fibrillation, valvular disease) as boolean.

These variables are well defined in the CDM [3].

2) Care process:

- Fitness (Levenshtein), as continuous numeric, represents the calculated distance between each trace and the normative trace;
- Duration trace (days), as continuous numeric, is the difference in days between the last and the first activity in the trace followed by each patient;
- Length of stay in hospital (in days), as continuous numeric, is the difference in days between the discharge and the admission to the hospital;
- Intervention, as categorical, can take the next values: None, fibrinolysis (if received fibrinolysis in hospital or thrombolysis in emergency care), thrombectomy mechanic (if received thrombectomy in hospital) or combined (if received fibrinolysis and thrombectomy)
- Rank trace, as categorical, represents the frequency of the path followed by the patient, being 1 the most frequent path. Values greater than 10 are consolidated into a value named 'Others'.
- Period, as continuous numeric, is defined as the month number of the patient's admission during the episode. We treat it as a continuous variable, ranging from 1 to 156 (the last month of the study period);
- Holiday, as boolean, is TRUE if admission was a holiday (Spain);
- Weekend, as boolean, is TRUE if admission was during weekend;
- Weekday, as categorical, day of the week on which admission occurred.

Finally, to specify the dependent variable, the event is TRUE if death during the first year of follow-up.

Figures

Figure S1. Small fragment of the event log for stroke case study.

case_id	activity_id	timestamp
...
11523	admission emergency care	2016-03-09 11:26:00
11523	ct mri	2016-03-09 11:28:18
11523	first asisstance medical	2016-03-09 11:36:06
11523	thrombolysis emergency	2016-03-09 13:18:00
11523	admission to observation ward	2016-03-09 14:41:23
11523	hospital admission date	2016-03-09 17:59:00
11523	discharge from emergency	2016-03-09 18:59:00
11523	hospital discharge date	2016-03-17 16:43:00
11522	admission emergency care	2013-05-09 13:00:00
11522	first asisstance medical	2013-05-09 13:16:49
11522	admission to observation ward	2013-05-09 16:32:30
11522	discharge from emergency	2013-05-09 21:23:00
...

Figure S2. Normative pathway in Petri Net format for stroke case study.

Note: Petri Net constructed from the interpretation of [11],[12],[13].

Figure S3. Process map for the most frequent traces covering 20% of the care pathway.

Figure S3.a) Process map for the most frequent traces covering 20% of the care pathway for diabetic patients with heart failure.

Legend: Process map covering the 20% most frequent care pathways followed by diabetic patients with heart failure within the diabetes cohort from Navarra, depicting the volume and time aspects of their treatment. The map's elements are:

- Nodes' name: set of prescribed treatments or whether the Hemoglobin A1C (HbA1C) measurement result met the control target (HBA<L) or not (HBA>L). Nodes named '_' indicate that no medication considered was prescribed.
- Nodes' number of days: Average time in days of the duration of the activity.
- Nodes' percentage: The proportion of cases in which the activity was executed.
- Arrows' number: The absolute number of activity instance executions.
- Arrows' percentage: The proportion of cases in which source and target activities were executed directly following each other.

Figure S3.b) Process map for the most frequent traces covering 20% of the care pathway for stroke patients.

Legend: Process map for the 20% of the actual care pathway followed by all stroke patients within our cohort, depicting the volume and time aspects of their treatment. The map's elements are:

- Nodes' labels: Activity name executed by the patient.
- Nodes' number: The number of cases in which the activity was executed.
- Nodes' percentage: The proportion of cases in which the activity was executed.
- Arrows' number: Average time in hours (and days) between activities.

Figure S4. DM2 Treatment Algorithm's interpretation for diabetic patients with heart failure in Petri Net format.

Note: Petri Net constructed from the interpretation of [14].

Figure S5. Process map of the care pathway for stroke patients.

Legend: Process map for the actual care pathway followed by all stroke patients within our cohort, depicting the volume and time aspects of their treatment. The map's elements are:

- Nodes' labels: Activity name executed by the patient.
- Nodes' number: The number of cases in which the activity was executed.
- Nodes' percentage: The proportion of cases in which the activity was executed.
- Arrows' number: Average time in hours (and days) between activities.

Figure S6. Distance matrix's elbow method's graphic.

Figure S7. Feature importance in point p_8 previous to the activity thrombolysis in emergency.

Legend: Relative importance score of patient characteristics measured in point decision ‘p_8’ (the immediately previous point to ‘thrombolysis_emergency_dt’ activity in Figure 2) in the empirical process model for the stroke cohort, preceding thrombolysis in emergency. The importance parameter is estimated based on their contribution to the model at this specific decision point. Interpretation: As observed, the most relevant feature associated with the paths’ diversion is age, followed by hospital, having or not a prescription for antiaggregant drugs, and having or not hypertension, heart failure and atrial fibrillation. An example of a combination of these features to follow the path with the intervention would be: patients between 40 and 70 years of age, without hypertension, atrial fibrillation or antiaggregant prescriptions.

Figure S8. Kaplan-Meier survival curves for the 10 most frequent traces for stroke cohort.

Figure S9. Observed fitness traces for diabetic patients with heart failure.

Tables

Table S1. COX model summary for stroke case study (Hazard Ratio (confidence interval (CI) 99%) and p-value).

Variable	Hazard Ratio	Lower CI 99%	Upper CI 99%	p-value
Patient attributes				
Age (years)	1.06921	1.06485	1.07358	0
Sex				
Male	Reference			
Female	0.90327	0.84483	0.96576	0
Prescription				
Antiarrhythmics	1.04777	0.9452	1.16147	0.243
Antihypertensive	0.96944	0.76368	1.23063	0.738
Antiaggregants	1.10589	1.02499	1.19318	0.001
Fibrinolytics	NA	NA	NA	NA
Comorbidities				
Heart failure	1.64353	1.51479	1.78321	0
Hypertension	1.04231	0.95835	1.13362	0.204
Diabetes	1.11555	1.04043	1.1961	0
Atrial fibrillation	1.28739	1.18428	1.39947	0
Valvular disease	1.15993	1.05602	1.27406	0
Care process				
Fitness (Levenshtein)	0.62916	0.43989	0.89986	0.001
Duration trace	1.00005	0.99925	1.00086	0.87
Length of stay in hospital	1.00718	1.00355	1.01081	0
Intervention				
None	Reference			

Fibrinolysis	0.86379	0.75573	0.9873	0.005
Thrombectomy mechanic	1.31412	0.90634	1.90537	0.058
Combined	1.0756	0.62635	1.84709	0.728
Rank trace				
Rank trace (1)	Reference			
Rank trace (2)	0.9743	0.83121	1.14201	0.673
Rank trace (3)	1.32199	1.08132	1.61624	0
Rank trace (4)	1.05664	0.84641	1.31907	0.522
Rank trace (5)	1.51695	1.24648	1.8461	0
Rank trace (6)	1.09938	0.8797	1.37392	0.274
Rank trace (7)	1.28253	1.02738	1.60104	0.004
Rank trace (8)	1.11445	0.87059	1.42661	0.258
Rank trace (9)	1.26918	0.99401	1.62052	0.012
Rank trace (10)	0.91305	0.68793	1.21184	0.408
Rank trace (Others)	1.07695	0.95361	1.21624	0.116
Period	1.00097	1.00002	1.00193	0.009
Holiday	1.0619	0.85743	1.31512	0.469
Weekend	0.96224	0.85037	1.08884	0.423
Weekday				
Sunday	Reference			
Monday	0.98121	0.87126	1.10504	0.681
Tuesday	1.0035	0.89045	1.13091	0.94
Wednesday	0.9752	0.86475	1.09975	0.59
Thursday	0.94465	0.83668	1.06655	0.227
Friday	NA	NA	NA	NA
Saturday	1.08828	0.96026	1.23338	0.082

Table S2. Summary of proportional hazard model (Weibull distribution) for diabetic patients with heart failure.

Variable	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% Confidence Interval (Lower, Upper)
Age	1.02	(0.99, 1.05)
Sex		
Female	Reference	
Male	1.32	(0.60, 2.92)
Class		
2	Reference	
1	6.89	(1.69, 28.02)
Charlson	1.27	(0.57, 2.82)

Table S3. Log-rank test the 10 most frequent traces for stroke case study.

Trace 1	Trace 2	p-value
1	5	0.0000
2	5	0.0000
4	5	0.0000
6	5	0.0000
8	5	0.0000
10	5	0.0000
1	9	0.0003
1	3	0.0003
7	1	0.0005
3	5	0.0009
2	9	0.0016
7	5	0.0017
2	3	0.0027
2	7	0.0039
4	9	0.0068
3	4	0.0162
6	9	0.0162
7	4	0.0168
9	5	0.0231
6	3	0.036
7	6	0.0362
10	9	0.0729
1	8	0.0732
8	9	0.1095
10	3	0.1493

10	7	0.1569
2	8	0.1887
7	8	0.2234
3	8	0.2384
10	1	0.2845
8	4	0.2908
6	8	0.4091
6	1	0.4383
2	10	0.5139
2	1	0.5447
10	4	0.5651
3	9	0.5701
1	4	0.5829
7	9	0.6129
10	8	0.7265
2	6	0.7327
10	6	0.7505
6	4	0.8303
2	4	0.9308
7	3	0.9535

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